

Investigation into Students' Understanding of Graphs Representing a Qualitative Scenario

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We have investigated students' understanding of graphs relating to qualitative scenarios. The students in question were first year undergraduate science students doing non-physics majors. The students (~300) were split into five groups; each group was given a different set of questions comprising a qualitative description of a physical scenario. In each case we asked students to draw a graph representing the motion involved, and to explain why they had chosen to draw the graph as they had. This study has allowed us to gain an insight into what students attend to as they draw these graphs. In this paper, we present empirical results of an analysis of the overall shape of the students' graphs and their accompanying explanations. Our findings show that students are much more likely to draw straight line graphs than curves (even when a curve is more appropriate) and that their reasoning is greatly dependent on context.

Keywords: physics education, graphs, qualitative graphs, graph construction

Introduction

Being able to draw and interpret graphs is undoubtedly a very important part of both mathematics and science. Deacon (1999) discusses the importance of being able to draw graphs and not being overly reliant on graphing software. In an Irish context, the importance of graphs is clear as they feature in the primary school curriculum and the Junior Cycle Maths and Science specifications (NCCA, 1999, 2015, 2018). Many studies have examined students' understanding of distance-time graphs in quantitative scenarios (Wemyss & van Kampen, 2013; Hale, 2000). In this paper we focus on students' conceptualisation of qualitative scenarios.

There is a large body of research in relation to students' abilities of both constructing and interpreting graphs. Overviews of existing research were carried out by both Leinhardt *et al* (1990) and Glazer (2011). However, few of these studies focus solely on construction tasks involving qualitative data. One such study where students are asked to construct graphs based on qualitative statements was carried out by Hattikudur *et al* (2012), however their study focuses solely on linear graphs and students' understanding of the y -intercept.

The research was carried out in an Irish university involving first year undergraduate science students enrolled in a Physics for General Science module. In this empirical paper we describe the methods used and the results obtained from this study so far.

Methods

The students involved in this study were first year undergraduate students, who were non-physics majors enrolled in the module Physics for General Science. 328 students were

studied, and these were split into 5 groups. Each group was given a different set of paired questions in an end of semester exam. Figures 1 and 2 show an example of the paired questions involving a ball rolling down a track; Figures 3 and 4 a beaker being filled with water. The students' responses were coded according to graph shape and their accompanying explanations.

We are interested not only in the accuracy of the students' responses but also in their reasoning. We used open coding techniques (Otero and Harlow, 2019) to capture the students' explanations. In many cases students' responses were fragmented. For this reason we chose students' separate arguments as the unit of analysis, rather than their responses in their entirety. Initially two principal researchers independently coded the same two sets of ten responses (one relating to a track question, the other to a beaker question) and discussed their codes. Once the key features to code for had been established, we started to develop a codebook in an iterative way (Anfara et al., 2002). The codebook was refined by again independently coding two different sets of student responses, taking care that as much as possible of the students' responses could be captured in simple dichotomous codes. After both parties agreed on the usability of the codebook, a third principal investigator used their finalised codebook to code a sample of responses to test for validity and found it worked very well. While this kind of inductive coding is not necessarily tied to a theoretical framework, it aligns well with our constructivist views of education, in that we seek to identify what aspects of the given data and the qualitative graphs the students constructed they attended to, and what bits of knowledge they activate in their reasoning.

The Activity – Track Questions

Three of the five groups were given paired questions involving a marble rolling down a frictionless track. They were asked to complete two position versus time graphs. All three groups were given an experimental setup diagram with an accompanying paragraph of text which explicitly said that the track was frictionless, points a, b and c were evenly spaced, and that the stopwatch was started when the marble reached point a. They were asked to continue the accompanying graph (Figure 1) and to explain why they had completed that graph that way. The groups were then given one of three different tracks, and were again asked to complete a position-time graph representing the motion of the marbles and to explain what they drew. These tracks are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1.

Experimental set-ups in the first of the paired questions. (i) Initial experimental setup for track questions, and (ii) accompanying position-time graph for track questions.

Figure 2.

Experimental set-ups in the second of the paired questions. Students were given one of these three settings. (i) step-down track, (ii) downward sloped track, (iii) upward sloped track.

The Activity – Beaker Questions

The other two groups were given paired questions involving water flowing into a beaker at a constant rate. Here, they were asked to complete two water level versus time graphs. Each group was given an experimental setup diagram with an accompanying piece of text stating that water flowed into the beaker as a constant stream, points a, b, and c were evenly spaced on the beaker, and that the stopwatch was started when the water reached level a. They were asked to continue the accompanying graph (Figure 3) and to explain why they had drawn it that way. Following this, each of the groups were given one of two different beakers and were again asked to complete a water level-time graph showing the change in height of the water. These beakers are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3.

Experimental set-ups in the first of the paired questions. (i) Initial experimental setup for beaker questions, and (ii) accompanying water level-time graph for beaker questions.

Figure 4.

Experimental set-ups in the second of the paired questions. Students were given one of these two settings. (i) half-cylinder in beaker, (ii) cone in beaker.

Data Analysis

Analysis of Drawings

In an initial examination of the graphs students drew, we noticed several trends that seemed to be applicable regardless of the context (track/beaker) or situation (shape of track/shape of object inside the beaker). We developed a set of independent and unambiguous categories of student drawings that was present in each data set. These categories were: *continues slope* (the student continued the line from a-b through to c); *steeper line* (the student drew a linear segment from b to c with a steeper slope than from a to b); *flatter line* (the student decided to draw a linear segment from b to c with a smaller slope than from a to b); *upward curve* (the student drew a curved line segment between b and c that increased in slope); and *downward curve* (the student drew a curved line segment with a decreasing slope). These categories were applicable to all data sets and, of the 312 total responses, these categories described all but 51 responses. In the step-down track setting, 12 students drew a line segment from b to c parallel in slope to that from a to b, but with a ‘kink’ or inflection at point b. We coded these responses as *parallel slope*. The remaining 39 responses we categorised as *other*.

Analysis of Explanations

On first examination of the responses, we noted that many students referred to the shape of the graph, the speed of the ball or the water level, and the end point. Sometimes students referred to graphical aspects (“I drew a curved graph because...”), sometimes to physical quantities (“the ball has constant speed”), sometimes to experimental features (“the cone is getting narrower”). Some students mentioned a reason or mechanism (“there is no friction, “gravity speeds the ball up”, “the water flow is constant”). In our first attempt at systematic coding, we created three overarching categories: *shape*, *(initial) rate of change*, and *end point*. All three partial responses above would be categorised under *shape*, since they contain a reference to either the shape of the graph or to a physical or experimental feature that corresponds to it. The category *(initial) rate of change* refers to the speed of the ball or the rate of change of the water level at point b; the word “initial” only applies to curved graphs. In each of those overarching categories we checked whether students referred to graphical, physical, or experimental features. Finally, in a separate category we coded whether students mentioned a *mechanism*, making for a total of ten dichotomous categories.

Two of the investigators independently coded the same sample of ten responses to one of the paired questions involving a beaker, plus the same sample of ten responses to one of the paired questions involving a track. During individual coding and discussion of the codes it emerged that the categories captured the data quite well, but that some refinement of the categories would capture the responses better. The investigators also noted that they often asked themselves similar questions to determine whether a response should be coded as comprising a category. We established a codebook to provide a more robust set of criteria for coders to help them decide if responses referred to graphical, physical, or experimental features within the overarching categories of *overall trend*, *(initial) rate of change at b*, and *interval to be covered*,

plus reference to a mechanism. For each of these ten categories the codebook, shown in Table 1, we provided a small number of questions coders could ask themselves.

The two principal investigators independently coded two new sets of 10 responses. They found that the codebook was easy to use, and that the ten zeros (not present) and ones (present) generated for each qualitative answer generally captured students' responses comprehensively and efficiently. The third investigator then applied the codebook to the same sample of responses to test the validity of the codebook. A Cohen's Kappa calculation on a subset of the data returned a value of 0.71 indicated excellent agreement.

Table 1.

Final version of the codebook used to analyse written explanations.

category		criteria/questions
overall trend	graphical	Do students mention the overall shape of the graph (straight or curved)? Do not code here for e.g. a kink at point b.
	physical	Do students say something about the speed being constant or that it speeds up or slows down throughout the process? Do not code if there is only a comparison to the speed on a-b.
	experimental	Do students say that after the step-down track, the track from b-c is flat/horizontal or sloped? Do students say that the cone gets narrower throughout b-c so that the volume is reducing as the water rises? Do students say that there is a new constant volume after the half cylinder?
(initial) rate of change at b	graphical	Do students compare their line to the initial line by using words such as: it got steeper / flatter / shallower, it curved up/down?
	physical	Do students describe the motion of the ball/rate of change of the water level by using words such as gets faster/slower, speeds up/slows down? Look for a distinction between a-b and b-c as opposed to the motion changing throughout b-c
	experimental	Do students comment on the change in the setup such as: there is a ramp / there is no cylinder in b-c / the track slopes?
interval to be covered	graphical	Do students discuss the length of the line? Do students discuss the interval between a-b and b-c in terms of the axes?
	physical	Do students discuss the overall time taken or distance travelled by using words such as "it took longer" / "more distance covered in less time" / "it takes more time"?
	experimental	Do students discuss the total volume of water needed or use words such as "to fill the beaker"? Do students discuss the length of the track (which they may call "the distance" but not "the distance travelled") or height of the beaker?
mechanism		Do students refer to gravity / force / friction / constant stream of water?

To illustrate the coding process, we will discuss how we coded a student’s written explanation to the graph they drew in response to the beaker question of Figure 4a: “*The line from b-c would still be straight as the stream is continuous. However, the volume to be filled by water in level b-c is now greater than level a-b because of the absence of the cylinder. It would take more time to fill b-c because the volume to be occupied has increased and so the slope would be less steep.*”. In this case:

- “the line from b-c would still be straight” is coded as 1 under *overall trend graphical*
- “the stream is continuous” is coded as 1 under *mechanism*
- “the volume to be filled by water in level b-c is now greater than level a-b” is coded as 1 under *interval to be covered experimental*
- “the absence of the cylinder” is coded as 1 under *(initial) rate of change at b experimental*
- “It would take more time to fill b-c” is coded as 1 under *interval to be covered physical*
- “the volume to be occupied has increased” was already coded
- “the slope would be less steep” is coded as 1 under *(initial) rate of change at b graphical*

Table 2.

Sample coded response. G = Graphical, P = Physical, E = Experimental.

overall trend			(initial) rate of change at b			interval to be covered			mechanism
G	P	E	G	P	E	G	P	E	
1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1

Table 2 summarises how we coded this response. All 312 responses were coded in this way; a sample of responses were coded independently by multiple researchers to ensure the codebook is reliable and valid.

Results

In this paper we focus on the responses to the second question given to each group. We have analysed both the graphs the students drew and their written explanations. Firstly, the responses were categorised according to the shape the students drew. In Table 3, the correct shape for each group is in bold.

One of the key findings from categorising the data in this way is that a large fraction of students drew straight lines when a curve is required. This is seen most clearly in the downwards sloped track group, where over double the number of students (58% vs 25%) drew a steeper straight line as opposed to an upwards curve. We also saw a high percentage of straight lines instead of curves in the cone beaker group and the upwards sloped track group, though less frequently than with the downwards sloped track group. The students’ written responses were coded according to the codebook shown in Table 1. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 3.

Percentage of student responses categorised by shape.

	step-down track (n=59)	downward sloped track (n=62)	upward sloped track (n=69)	half cylinder in beaker (n=74)	cone in beaker (n=64)
continues slope	14	14	9	9	6
parallel slope	12	0	0	0	0
steeper line	58	58	1	2	10
flatter line	6	2	33	75	43
upward curve	5	25	1	0	7
downward curve	0	0	38	0	34
other	5	2	16	14	2

Table 4.

Percentage of responses that contain each argument. G = graphical, P = physical, E = experimental.

group	overall trend			(initial) rate of change at b			interval to be covered			mechanism
	G	P	E	G	P	E	G	P	E	
step-down track	7	27	3	15	100	93	0	31	3	22
downward sloped track	10	10	0	18	87	87	0	39	0	23
upward sloped track	20	20	0	10	81	90	0	33	7	33
half-cylinder in beaker	9	14	3	20	27	72	4	69	77	24
cone in beaker	19	17	23	9	17	61	6	70	67	17

From Table 4 we can see that students in the track groups place a much higher importance on discussing the initial rate of change of the motion in comparison to the beaker students who favour writing about the interval to be covered. Our initial interpretation is that the main resources that are activated by the students are those relating to the change in the rate of change of the position at point b, or the total time the process takes from b to c. Thus, in situations where students should draw a curve, they tend to draw straight lines because they only consider what happens at b or at c, and not in between.

Conclusions

The two main findings of this study thus far are that a large proportion of the students drew straight line graphs rather than curves, and that the students’ reasoning depends greatly on the context of the question. In the next stage of this study we will interview students so as to delve deeper into their reasoning and to further our understanding of why they chose to

draw the graphs that they did. We will also provide a new set of different graphing questions that deal with resistance. We will vary the orientation to see if that makes a difference in terms of students' ability to plot position on the axis. One group will receive a selection of possible graphs and be asked to describe what caused them to select a certain graph over the other. This aims to see if when students are given the resources, are they better able to activate them than when they are asked to draw the graphs themselves.

Data Availability Statement

The data from this study is available from the authors upon reasonable request. The ethical approval number is DCUREC/2022/185.

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